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Evaluation & Impact Assessment INDICATOR DASHBOARDS

<p>MAA Scenario</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>At any stage of the implementation.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>Large</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>High, advanced quantitative and IT skills needed.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>Depends on the data volume.</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>PC and software access, data collection costs if not available.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tool # 34, 35, 37.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC (OF THE TOOL)

Purpose

Indicator dashboards are used to:

- Monitor innovation performance of the projects, programmes, portfolios or countries
- Enable performance comparison between entities
- Assess the impact of R&I outputs
- Enable predictive modeling.

Background and Logic

Indicators and dashboards (indices) are frequently used to monitor innovation of the programmes and projects. They typically consist of multiple indicator layers – composite indicators, which attempt to describe complex reality, in which the interventions are implemented. They are frequently used in order to assess and compare performance over time and between different stakeholders. We will support the application of the two most established dashboards in the area of agricultural innovation: IFPRI ASTI and OECD Frascati Manual.

Agricultural Science and Technology Indicators (ASTI)

An evaluation framework developed by the International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI). ASTI collects and shares data on institutional developments, investments, and capacity in agricultural Research and Development (R&D) at national, regional, and global levels for low-and middle-income countries. ASTI also produces reports and publication describing trends in human and financial capacity in agricultural R&D at national levels, along with information on comparative agricultural R&D performance across countries and regions. Benchmarking tools enable cross-country comparisons and rankings of key spending and researcher indicators. Indicators from this framework can be used as resources for the selection of indicators for evaluation of Research and Innovation (R&I) projects and portfolios. The comprehensive database allows monitoring the progress of a project against the benchmarks. They can be found on a dedicated website coordinated by the CGIAR. Useful resources: www.asti.cgiar.org

OECD Manuals

The OECD is an important player involved into development of Science and Technology (S&T) evaluation dashboards. Two of them, which are most relevant for our requirements are the Frascati Manual (2015) and the Oslo Manual developed by the OECD with Eurostat (2018).

The dashboards provide a comprehensive overview of the data collection in terms of specific indicators at the national level. Additional background information on agriculture-related indicators can be found in these specific OECD documents on measuring agricultural innovation investments:

Frascati Manual

<https://www.oecd.org/sti/inno/frascati-manual.htm>

Oslo Manual

<https://www.oecd.org/science/oslo-manual-2018-9789264304604-en.htm>

<https://www.oecd.org/agriculture/topics/agricultural-productivity-and-innovation/documents/analysing-policies-to-improve-agricultural-productivity-growth-sustainably.pdf>

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